

How renewable can green ammonia be? Natural resources exergy footprint on a small-scale ammonia production system

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ABSTRACT

The world energy transition state has significantly increased the weight of renewables infrastructure importance on the development of new energy production systems. This study presents a novel perspective on the production of green ammonia by investigating how renewable it can be based on renewable and non-renewable exergy costs. The primary objective of this research is to verify how the exergy costs of renewable (sunlight, wind, water, and soil) and non-renewable resources (fossil fuels, white hydrogen, and critical raw materials) affect the physical requirements for ammonia production via the Haber-Bosch process under different loads and resources availability conditions. Additional objectives involve comparing the costs of producing ammonia under different plant load operation conditions with the stream recirculation strategy and evaluating how the hybridization of electricity sources affect both the plant load strategy and the flexibility versus efficiency dilemma. The circular thermoeconomic model developed on Aspen Plus and integrated with TAESLab explores ammonia production on a small-scale integrated multi-product ammonia plant with different sources of electricity (based on IEA NZE for solar PV, wind, and grid), hydrogen (white and green via alkaline, proton and anion-exchange, and solid oxide electrolysis), nitrogen (cryogenic), water, and soil (exergy). Our innovative methodology includes the exergy costs of the processes and materials required for each technology infrastructure construction. Our findings shed a light on how renewable ammonia's physical costs affect its current and future projected applications based on its overall specific exergy cost (SEC). These values ranged between 13.0 and 44.0 MWh/t_{NH₃} depending on the adopted pathway. Therefore, this work highlights the required energy transition impact on the small-scale ammonia production for regions with different natural resources availability on the world.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current energy transition towards renewable energy sources projects sustainable ammonia production as of fundamental importance to decarbonize several sectors of our society. Not only ammonia has direct applications as a refrigerant or cleaning agent, but also is highly demanded in agriculture for fertilizers production (chemical precursor for urea, ammonium nitrate and sulfate, monoammonium and diammonium phosphates) (H2Europe, 2023; IRENA and AEA, 2022; Ishaq and Crawford, 2024). These applications, combined with its novel prospected usages (energy vector/carrier and storage, CO₂ capture sorbent, carbon-free fuel for fuel-cells, gas turbines (GTs), internal combustion engines (ICEs) and maritime applications, in gasification and water purification, and hydrogen provider for catalytic cracking), shed a light on how ammonia will keep playing a role as the second most demanded chemical in the world (157-180 Mt/year currently and 680 Mt/year in 2050) (H2Europe, 2023; IRENA and AEA, 2022). However, its high carbon footprint (around 2.8 tonCO₂/ton NH₃) (Chehade and Dincer, 2021) highlights a clear need to link ammonia production to natural resources consumption efficiency to evaluate its renewability and reach sustainable production for the future ahead of us (Mingolla and Rosa, 2025).

Small-scale renewable ammonia plants (de la Hera et al., 2024; Koschwitz et al., 2024; Sánchez and Martín, 2018; Sun et al., 2024) have been thoroughly presented as a viable alternative to speed up the fertilizers decarbonization transition by covering local/regional production without high CAPEX costs and mitigating logistic and storage operational costs. These plants face these extra challenges than high-scale ones besides the renewable electricity intermittency that causes dynamic behavior (Fahr et al., 2025; Laimon and Goh, 2024; Smith and Torrente-Murciano, 2024; Song et al., 2025). Recently, demonstration small-scale green ammonia plants have begun operating in the world (e.g., in Ramme, Denmark), but the land proportions required by the renewable energy sources (wind and solar PV) are a fundamental aspect that should be better investigated to mitigate land occupation, transformation and soil exergy waste.

Exergy is a thermodynamic property capable of evaluating the irreversibility of any macroscopic process, even those related to renewable energy sources (Lima, Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2025; Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024). The inclusion of required materials, chemicals and infrastructures via life cycle analysis (LCAs)

(Comission, 2024) on the overall exergy costs of a product (Bicer et al., 2016) allows both delving into its overall degree of sustainability and provides a thorough evaluation on demanded non-renewable and renewable natural resources consumption (Granovskii et al., 2007; Thomassen et al., 2024). More specifically, other methods have also presented different perspectives on renewable electricity, hydrogen and ammonia production to evaluate their overall planetary (D'Angelo et al., 2021), carbon, economic (Mayer et al., 2023), energy (Müller et al., 2024) and exergy footprints (Mendrela et al., 2024; Sciubba, 2024). Therefore, proper evaluation of non-renewable and renewable exergy costs allows the evaluation of the renewability of ammonia in a context where even renewable energy sources lifespans add up irreversibilities to ammonia-dependent cradle-to-grave chain production physical costs.

Natural hydrogen is a non-renewable natural resource that might play a significant role as an energy vector on the decarbonization of several industries and significantly reduce economical costs (estimated currently around 1\$/kg_{H₂}) of hydrogen production and other chemicals (Blay-Roger et al., 2024). However, it is still very uncertain the wells productivity, H₂ concentration and economic viability. There is currently a lack of public data about discovered wells, with a few publications about techno-economical analyses (Mathur et al., 2025; Musa et al., 2024). However, natural hydrogen already raises expectations on its potential and how it would affect highly-dependent H₂ industries, such as the ammonia one by allowing better plant load control for non-carbonaceous ammonia production and the physical costs associated with it.

Like water and minerals, soil is a valuable yet finite natural resource (Alvarenga et al., 2013). Its irreversible degradation poses a significant challenge to global food security (EC and EEA, 2024). Moreover, soil plays a crucial role in the energy transition and decarbonization of our planet (Tonelli et al., 2023), serving as the foundation for forests and renewable energy infrastructures. Assessing the value of land is a complex problem that can be approached from multiple perspectives. Healthy soils provide a wide range of ecosystem services, making their evaluation essential for sustainable management. In previous studies, exergy has been proposed as a key indicator for assessing soil systems (Palacino et al., 2022; Valero et al., 2020, 2022). To establish a reference for optimal soil fertility, the concept of Pristinia was introduced — an idealized state representing maximized fertility, free from degradation. This reference environment allows for the systematic assignment of exergy values to any given soil, providing a quantitative measure of its productivity. In contrast, Thanatia represents the ultimate degraded state of soil, devoid of life and biological activity. The establishment of Pristinia, also referred to as "OptSOIL", enables the quantification of exergy content in optimally fertile soils. This is achieved by comparing their chemical composition, concentration, and comminution exergy with that of Thanatia, the dispersed and degraded reference state.

The main goal of this study is to evaluate how renewable ammonia production can be based on natural resources non-renewable and renewable exergy costs throughout a small-scale plant lifetime. We applied the exergy cost of electricity (ExCOE) methodology (Lima, Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2025; Lima, Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2025; Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024) to evaluate how these renewable (sunlight, wind, water, and air) and non-renewable (fossil fuels, soil, white hydrogen, and critical raw materials) aspects affect the physical requirements for this plant under different hydrogen availabilities (recirculation for plant load control) and resources availability conditions. Additionally, we shed a light on the flexibility versus efficiency dilemma green ammonia plants (GAPs) face and evaluate how electricity sources hybridization affect ammonia renewability. Our innovative methodology applies a circular thermoeconomic model (via open-source TAESLab) of our plant modeled in Aspen Plus v14 to include the exergy costs (renewable and non-renewable) of the processes and materials required by combining life-cycle analyses and process modeling for each technology infrastructure construction. Our findings focus on two aspects: How renewable can ammonia be? And the flexibility versus efficiency dilemma; These emphasize how natural non-renewable resources and infrastructure costs propagate through ammonia chain production.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Model and plant description

Our model focuses on a small-scale industrial complex of green hydrogen and ammonia production. It encompasses a on-grid hybrid wind-solar photovoltaic (PV) plant combined with an electrolyzer of distinct technologies (AWE, PEM, SOEC, or AEM), a cryogenic air separation unit (ASU) (Aneke and Wang, 2015) and a small-scale green ammonia plant (10053 t_{NH₃}/year). This plant is assumed as commissioned in 2025 and operates during 25 years for 8760 h per year. Our objective is to evaluate how ammonia's physical costs will change over time for this specific plant, according to its natural resources availability and demand (water, sun, wind, soil) based on the exergy cost of electricity (ExCOE) methodology. Figure 1 summarizes this study based on the ExCOE our group has recently published (Lima, Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2025; Lima, Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2025; Lima

et al., 2024; Torrubia, Lima, et al., 2024; Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024). Here we expanded our analysis by including exergy costs of soil/land occupation and water for electrolytic hydrogen production. Additionally, we have included an estimate of exergy costs of natural/geologic hydrogen (also called gold or white) based on available public technical information (extraction and H₂ purification) on literature (Mathur et al., 2025; Musa et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Representative diagram of the ExCOE method applied to the small-scale green ammonia plant inputs of this study. Orange represents the renewable and non-renewable natural resources required by the plant: sun, wind, soil, water, and mines (minerals and fossil fuels). Gold represents the natural hydrogen extraction, green the electrolytic hydrogen production, gray the nitrogen air separation unit and the electricity grid and blue the ammonia synthesis production.

Figure 2 details the process flow diagram (PFD) of our adopted small-scale green ammonia synthesis plant. The adopted Haber-Bosch configuration involves an intercooled two-compression process (to 100 and 200 bar) followed by pre-heating to adjust the syngas stream to react under stoichiometric conditions (3:1 H₂:N₂) in a two-bed reactor loaded with a Fe-C catalyzer (Lima, Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2025). After NH₃ conversion, the product stream heats the reactant stream before being completely cooled down to 300K and 240K in a two-stage separator at 180 and 30 bar, respectively. 1% of the vapor second separator (SEP2) is purged to avoid Argon (Ar) accumulation whereas the remainder is properly recycled (streams 24 and 25). Cooling water is first used to control the syngas mixture temperature (HEX1, HEX2 and HEX4) and then expands to 1 bar, to partially recover some exergy and increase the plant efficiency. This plant configuration contains a recirculation circuit (streams 8 to 10) that is used by the control system to regulate the plant load due to intermittent renewable electricity/upstream hydrogen availability. Valve VLV1 is used to regulate the recirculated syngas to the upstream compressor pressure COMP1. This adopted strategy has been adopted to commercial ammonia plant providers to regulate the plant operation due to intermittent hydrogen availability.

The authors modeled the presented plant model in Aspen PLUS v14 where the mass, chemical species and energy balances were properly solved. Next, the authors evaluated the chemical and thermomechanical aspects of exergy streams in an in-house MatLab code and used TAESLab MatLab package to evaluate the circular thermoeconomic analysis (Lima, Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2025; Lima et al., 2024) for all steady-state plant loads between 10% and 100% relative to the nominal H₂ molar flow rate ($\dot{n}_{\text{nom.,H}_2}(1) = 106.9 \text{ kmol}_{\text{H}_2}/\text{h}$). Some details about the plant specification are available on Tab. 1 and on (Lima, Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2025; Lima et al., 2024). More details about the plant load are presented on Sec. 3.1. After modeling, the ExCOE method is used to evaluate how the plant's input non-renewable and renewable exergy costs affect ammonia overall cost under specific conditions throughout its lifetime.

2.2 ExCOE methodology

This ExCOE methodology is based on physical allocation to evaluate the energy and carbon intensities of the processes of mining and concentration (M & C), smelting and refining (S & R) of all the materials (Torrubia

Figure 2: Process flow diagram (PFD) of a small-scale green ammonia plant (GAP) with a recirculation circuit (from streams 8 to 10) to intermittent renewable electricity/hydrogen load control. Presented values represent temperature (K), pressure (bar) and molar flow rate (kmol/h) at nominal load conditions.

et al., 2023) required on the infrastructures of most adopted primary energy sources (PES) of the world. The decarbonization and energy transition towards renewables have unraveled a change of perspective towards critical raw material-based technologies, thereby increasing the weight of infrastructures (and material intensity) on overall electricity production costs. These PES are classified between non-renewable (fossil fuels, natural gas, oil, coal, and nuclear) and renewable sources (hydroelectric, biomass, wind, and solar photovoltaic) and the ExCOE methodology allow us to evaluate the overall exergy costs of producing 1 kW of electricity from each of them (Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2024) for the past and for future energy transition scenarios, such as the NZE, APC, and STATES (IEA, 2024a, 2024b). The superior part of Fig. 1 summarizes this method by allowing us to evaluate the non-renewable and renewable exergy costs of each individual PES and the electricity grid over time. This information is used to analyze how these costs propagate over all sectors that demand electricity. Recently published papers (Lima, Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2025; Lima, Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2025; Lima et al., 2024; Torrubia, Lima, et al., 2024) adopt this method to evaluate the costs of chemicals like hydrogen and ammonia, however it can be used for any product.

With respect to electrolytic hydrogen production, we adopted here an extended analysis of a recently published paper (Lima, Torrubia, Valero, and Valero, 2025) that accounted for the material intensities of distinct electrolyzer technologies (Wei et al., 2024). We expanded our method by including exergy costs of pumping water ($\eta_{Pump} = 0.65$) to the current steady-state operation pressure of each studied electrolyzer technology unit (30, 50, 1 and 35 bar for AWE, PEM, SOEC, and AEM, respectively) and subsequent hydrogen compression to 700 bar ($\eta_{Comp} = 0.65$) (Granovskii et al., 2007). Recently, it was estimated a lifetime averaged AEM efficiency by including or disregarding cell degradation and O_2 as co-product, and the results ranged between 55.7% and 57.2% (Campbell-Stanway et al., 2025). Therefore, to avoid the complexity of modeling an electrolyzer over its entire lifetime and to simplify our analysis, weighted-lifetime average efficiencies were adopted (Fig. 3) over the plant lifetime based on state-of-the-art projected efficiencies up to 2050 (Chatenet et al., 2022). A comprehensive summary of all remaining assumptions is available on (Lima, Torrubia, Torres, et al., 2025).

We evaluated water exergy costs (Carrasquer et al., 2016) for three specific processes: pumping for electrolytic hydrogen production and cooling water for ammonia synthesis temperature control, and producing steam. Water costs for the natural H_2 extraction were not included here because the energy intensity already includes them in their analysis (Mathur et al., 2025). The nitrogen exergy costs assumed a cryogenic air separation unit (ASU) (Aneke and Wang, 2015) and used the electricity source available for the plant configuration (i.e., based on their ExCOE values). The electricity is assumed as originally sourced by the grid.

Figure 3: Lifetime-weighted average electrolyzers efficiency for AWE, PEM, SOEC, AEM.

2.3 Geologic/natural hydrogen exergy costs

In order to primarily estimate the exergy cost of geological/natural hydrogen, the authors used as reference the industrial plant configuration and energy intensities for raw H_2 presented by (Mathur et al., 2025). To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is currently a limited public data availability on natural H_2 production and modeling (Blay-Roger et al., 2024; Mathur et al., 2025), with only the former presenting technical simulation data about the extraction and purification processes. This uncertainty increases the need for assumptions to present an initial projection on H_2 non-renewable and renewable exergy costs. The proposed NH_3 purification process is described to provide commercially certified purity degree (99.9 vol%) by adopting the following processes: wellhead gas compression, water gas separation and sequential triethylene glycol (TEG) dehydration, H_2 PSA with titanium silicate molecular sieve, followed finally by final compression and cooling to hydrogen storage and/or transport. In short, the adopted aforementioned stages are similar to natural gas (NG), but focus on H_2 instead of methane (CH_4) or geothermal purification industries.

Based on this context, we adopted some assumptions for the natural hydrogen gas plant (Tab. 1). We adopted Peng-Robinson (PG-EoS) as representative equation of state. H_2S presence neglected because most geological NH_3 sites did not find them. Additionally, He presence and recovery neglected due to economic viability reasons (concentrations greater than 0.5 vol%). More assumptions can be found on Mathur et al., 2025.

Table 1: Plant technical specifications and assumptions

Green ammonia plant					
Plant lifetime (years)	25				
Electricity sources	Wind, PV, grid wind+PV, wind+grid, PV+grid, or wind+PV+grid (7)				
Hydrogen nominal molar flow rate (kmol/h)	106.92				
Nitrogen stream composition [kmol/kmol]	[99.0 vol% N_2 and 1.0 vol% Ar]				
Compressors isentropic efficiency [-]	0.75				
Separator pressures [bar]	150 and 30				
Quench flow ratio [-]	0.5				
Purge flow ratio [-]	0.01				
Electrolyzers					
Number of used state-of-the-art electrolyzers	AWE 3 (average)	PEM 2 (lowest)	SOEC 5 (highest)	AEM 5 (highest)	
Geologic/natural hydrogen gas plant (Mathur et al., 2025)					
Base wellhead exiting composition (vol%)	75.0 H_2	12.0 N_2	9.0 CH_4	2.0 CO_2	2.0 H_2O
Energy intensity (MJ/kg H_2)	NG	Oil	Coal	Electricity	
15.0 vol% H_2	0	0	0	62.5	
75.0 vol% H_2	0	0	0	8.5	

2.4 Soil exergy evaluation

The exergy assessment of topsoil fertility quantifies three key components: the inorganic fraction of the soil, soil organic matter (SOM), and microorganisms. The inorganic physical and chemical properties of soil are critical to its fertility. Soil texture, defined by the distribution of three primary particle sizes—sand, silt, and clay—is a fundamental physical parameter. The mineral composition of these textural fractions has been established, and their chemical exergy is determined using Szargut's reference environment (Szargut, 1989). By calculating the specific chemical exergy for each textural fraction, it is possible to assess the overall chemical exergy associated with soil texture. The concentration exergy of soil minerals is estimated by comparing their concentrations in the optimal fertility state (OptSOIL) with their average abundance in the Earth's crust, as represented in Thanatia (Valero and Valero, 2014). The concentration exergy of nutrients is derived from the difference between their concentrations in fertile soil and their baseline concentrations in the hydrosphere, which serves as the reference state. Only the most significant and readily quantifiable nutrients are considered in these calculations, including nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, copper, sodium, iron, manganese, and zinc (Valero et al., 2020). Soil Organic Matter (SOM) is a fundamental component of soil fertility, as it influences various physical, chemical, and biological properties. Based on recent advancements in the characterization of organic matter composition and empirical models for higher heating value (HHV), the exergy of SOM has been estimated at 19406.1 kJ/kg. This value provides a quantitative measure of the energy potential stored in SOM, further highlighting its critical role in sustaining soil productivity. The final soil component is the living fraction of organic matter (OM), that plays a crucial role in soil function and fertility. The eco-exergy of microbial biomass is estimated using Jørgensen's β factor, which accounts for the biological complexity and energy potential of microorganisms. Microbial concentration can be quantified through DNA-based techniques; however, when such data are unavailable, soil microbial carbon (C_{mic}) is typically assumed to constitute 2% of total organic carbon.

This methodological framework enables the integration of multiple factors influencing soil formation and degradation into a unified exergy-based metric, providing a comprehensive assessment of soil health and functionality. The exergy of Pristinia has been estimated at 309.4 toe/ha. Analyzing seven different agricultural soils from Aragón, Spain, the average exergy value obtained was 164.40 toe/ha (or 688.3 MJ/m²), with a range between 142 and 181 toe/ha (594.5 and 757.8 MJ/m²). This average value has been considered in this study as a reasonable first approximation of the exergy contained in real agricultural soils, which are far from the pristine state.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses on the results obtained by the aforementioned methodology. First, the authors present an analysis of the flexibility *versus* efficiency dilemma renewable ammonia plants need to constantly face on based on the plant load states and the external resources availability and costs. Then, we shed a light on how renewable ammonia can be based on the non-renewable and renewable exergy costs of required inputs. The importance of soil exergy and natural hydrogen evidences parameters that are fundamental for both a required decarbonization process and a fair and coherent energy transition pathway.

3.1 Flexibility x efficiency dilemma

To evaluate the possible range of steady state operations this ammonia plant can have, the authors used the recirculation circuit to evaluate the plant performance under 10 different loads between 10% and 100% $\dot{n}_{nom.,H_2}$. Fig. 4 summarizes our plant behavior under recirculation, recycle and exergetic perspectives. Fig. 4(a) shows that when the recirculation circuit takes place (plant load reduction), SPLIT1 flow rate ratio suddenly increases (blue line), causing irreversible pressure loss on valve V1 (red line) and a decrease in steam production (green line). These two exergy losses are highlighted by Fig. 4(c), where the exergy efficiency drops from 80 to almost 30%. The steam production reduction (blue bar nearly disappears on 10% load) thereby affects the exergy efficiency distribution between the products. Complementarily, Fig. 4(b) shows the non-linear effect of the recirculation circuit on the compression power, decreasing from 100% at nominal conditions to 22% at 10% load. This shows how mass flow rate circulates through the compressor without any other purpose besides load control, generating irreversibilities and increasing ammonia's exergy cost under partial loads. Finally, an important aspect is how exergy keeps revolving around the plant's streams (Fig. 4(d)): while mass recycle (black line) is mostly constant due to the compressor control system maintaining the system loaded at the same pressure, the exergy associated to the recycle circuit (streams 24 and 25) decreases (red line), showing how the plant lowers its capacity to deal with H₂ at very low load conditions. On the other hand, the exergy associated to the recirculated circuit (stream 8 to 10) significantly increases, but it is not well recovered, thus significantly increasing its contribution to the overall NH₃ plant irreversibility.

Figure 4: Small-scale renewable NH₃ plant behavior under distinct plant load conditions: (a) Recirculation effects on SPLIT1 ratio (black), and on normalized recirculation flow rate (blue), V1 irreversibility (red), and steam production (green). (b) Normalized compressor power. (c) Plant exergy efficiency discretized by each product's contributions. (d) Recycle circuit mass and exergy ratios (relative to H₂ and N₂ input rates) as well as recirculation circuit exergy ratio (relative only to H₂ input rate). All normalized values are related to each variable's maximum (e.g., highest compressor power at nominal load whereas maximum recirculation ratio at minimum load).

An extended thermoeconomic analysis on the plant load (Fig. 5) unravels how the processes irreversibilities take place on the plant performance. The dissipative components (HEX5, SEP3, and MIX4-5) are responsible for nearly 50% of all irreversibilities on 10% load and only 28% at nominal load. Due to the lower recycle mass rate at 10%, mixing components (MIX1-3) also take their part. At higher loads, the production components (SEP1-2 and FLASH) naturally causes more irreversibilities due to separating ammonia and steam under higher flow rates. Therefore, as mentioned before, there is a clear dilemma between flexibility and efficiency for renewable ammonia plants that require proper analysis on the external resources availability and their respective physical/exergetic, environmental and economical costs; and this is where our methodology can take place to highlight non-renewable and renewable exergy aspects to show how renewable ammonia can actually be.

3.2 How renewable can ammonia be under presented conditions?

To contextualize the concept of renewability adopted in this work, we mean by accumulating all non-renewable and renewable irreversibilities/exergy costs over the production of a product (ammonia in this case) to check its overall physical cost related to 1 exergy-based kJ of ammonia. Tab. 2 relates lifetime indicators for our small-scale ammonia plant. Regarding the soil exergy component, we assumed complete loss of exergy during the plant lifetime due to land transformation and occupation, as well as possible contamination over time. By combining the possible plant's renewables (Tab. 1) land occupation rates (35000 and 150000 m²/MW for PV and wind, respectively) (Mingolla et al., 2024) with our nominal required power components (approximately 13.8 MW), we estimate a surface area occupation range between 53.7 and 225.1 ha. (Tab. 2). This surface area corresponds to an unused soil for both ecological and agriculture applications, thereby this plant neglects the possibility of using its exergy (7074.5 MJ/h_{lifetime} soil exergy destroyed under maximum occupation for 23780 MJ/h ammonia production) throughout the plant lifetime. Therefore, the total amount of soil exergy lost to produce ammonia is of the same order of magnitude of all cumulative nominal ammonia exergy. And since usually post-industry soils have not been used for neither agricultural nor ecological activities, this represent a fully irreversible exergy destruction process.

Figure 5: Plant load irreversibilities per component function: (a) Absolute values (kW). (b) Normalized/relative values. Dissipative encompasses HEX5, SEP3, MIX4-5, whereas Mixing MIX1-3, Compression COMP1-2, Heat transfer HEX1-4, Reaction REAC1-2, and Production SEP1-2 and FLASH.

Based on these results, sustainable agriculture practices (e.g., agricultural/ecological practices with renewables production) with low-carbon ammonia production might be fundamental to unravel possibilities of respecting land occupation and water consumption global limits for hydrogen production (Tonelli et al., 2023) while decarbonizing the fertilizer sector and land footprints (Mingolla and Rosa, 2025) and minimizing non-renewable natural resources exergy consumption.

Table 2: Lifetime small-scale ammonia plant indicators

Green ammonia plant	
Commissioned power range (MW)	[13.8; 15.3]
Renewables occupied land range (ha)	[53.7; 225.1]
Overall and levelized soil exergy lost (MJ and MJ/h _{lifetime})	1.55x10 ⁹ — 7.07x10 ³
Cumulative nominal NH ₃ production and exergy (t _{NH₃} — MJ/h _{lifetime})	258.95x10 ³ — 23.78x10 ³
Number of state-of-the-art electrolyzer changes	AWE PEM SOEC AEM
	3 2 5 5

Based on different efficiencies for each possible electrolyzer technology (Fig. 3), we projected the demand of electrolyzers over the plant lifespan. PEM and AWE (high TRLs) would require at least two and three changes, respectively, whereas SOEC and AEM (low TRLs) would require at least 5. This means increased CAPEX costs and higher material footprint for these electrolyzers, although this update would allow more efficient hydrogen and ammonia production.

Figure 6 shows how overall specific exergy costs of ammonia production would behave over time under three different hydrogen production pathways: a hybrid wind + solar PV renewable plant with PEM electrolysis (best response to renewable electricity production variability) under nominal, medium and minimum loads, a on-grid

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6: Overall specific exergy costs (SEC, $\text{MWh}/\text{t}_{\text{NH}_3}$) of ammonia production under different hydrogen production pathways: (a) for PEM with hybrid wind + solar PV renewable; (b) for electricity grid with four distinct water splitting electrolyzer technologies; (c) for natural H_2 under different plant loads and H_2 concentrations.

plant at the IEA NZE scenario under nominal load and a natural H_2 fed plant under different loads and two different H_2 available concentrations (Mathur et al., 2025). As Fig. 6(a) shows, the minimum load (10%, red) exergy costs range between approximately 36.0 and 24.0 $\text{MWh}/\text{t}_{\text{NH}_3}$, thereby highlighting how the recirculation plant load control negatively affects the overall exergy cost in comparison to the others. Since these fully-renewable, off-grid plants depend on renewable energy availability, their physical costs will significantly fluctuate. This presents a flexibility-efficiency dilemma, where optimal conditions must be found between them to sustainably produce renewable ammonia. However, these exergy costs can fluctuate less with locally precise strategies to avoid reaching such a low load such as increasing renewables capacity factor with hybrid plants, significant energy (batteries) and hydrogen (tank) storages, and a very refined weather prediction to avoid non-renewable exergy usage waste, sustainably speaking.

A different view is the on-grid plant of Fig. 6(b), where depending on the electrolyzer technology, the exergy costs range between 21.0 and 17.0 (2025), and 10.0 and 8.0 MWh/t_{NH₃} (2050). SOEC and AEM present the best costs, but this comes with both technology uncertainty and low lifetimes. PEM and AWE, on the other hand, are less replaced over the plant lifetime and on the future start presenting similar exergy costs to the formers, but PEM currently depends on critical raw materials whereas AWE presents low future technology prospects and poor dynamic response (although the grid would provide stable electricity for the latter).

At last, Fig. 6(c) shows how plant load and wellhead hydrogen concentration will affect ammonia's exergy costs. Plant load exerts higher influence on the overall cost, increasing it up to almost 44.0 MWh/t_{NH₃} in 2025. On the other hand, 50% and 100% loads always present costs lower than 20.0 MWh/t_{NH₃}. Initial hydrogen concentration is a fundamental factor for viable (physical and economical) extraction, as currently 8.0 MWh/t_{NH₃} of extra costs can be seen between 15 vol% and 75%. Therefore, this aspect would naturally turn ammonia more expensive for future applications.

These results shed a light on how renewable ammonia can be over time, that is, how much exergy is required to produce 1 kJ of this chemical. Current ammonia's exergy costs ranged between 13.0 and 44.0 MWh/t_{NH₃}. These values can significantly vary depending on available renewable natural resources availability (sunlight, wind, water, soil, critical raw materials, chemicals, technological advancements, required pre-treatments, etc.), but shed a light on the renewability of a common chemical feedstock can affect the overall chain production.

3.3 Future work

Future works that benefit from this research involve evaluating possible streamlined usages of ammonia exergy costs, such as fertilizers (e.g., urea, ammonium nitrate (AN) or sulphate (AS), monoammonium and diammonium phosphate (MAP and DAP)), chemical precursor and feedstock, energy vector or storage (evaluate loss over time), fuel, and others. The soil exergy can contribute on answering possible soil usage applications: biodiversity and CO₂ capture loss, renewables production or food production?

Plant-wise, exergy costs from infrastructures of alternative separation methods should be explored for gas purification and co-products (PSA, absorption or membranes). Also, optimal purge gases recovery can provide interesting co-products and syngas recovery. Including the chemical plant infrastructure requirements should also contribute to evaluate the material intensity of renewable ammonia, especially to evaluate dynamic load exergy costs under local environmental conditions. Finally, novel plant configurations (optimize steam production and auxiliary refrigeration cycle), electrolytic ammonia production and natural hydrogen plant infrastructure exergy costs should also be tested to improve technical viability to ammonia and other chemical feedstocks production.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the authors delve into presenting a new perspective on the production of renewable ammonia in a small-scale industrial plant by investigating its renewability based on renewable and non-renewable exergy costs. We also included soil exergy as a novel parameter on the circular thermoeconomical analysis and presented initial estimations on natural hydrogen overall exergy costs. The following conclusions can be drawn from our analysis:

- Flexibility *versus* efficiency dilemma: The adopted strategy of plant load control causes significant efficiency reduction (from 80 to 30%) for an ammonia plant due to renewables intermittency;
- How renewable?: Current ammonia's exergy costs range depending on the adopted pathway between 13.0 and 44.0 MWh/t_{NH₃}, indicating how renewable this product can currently be.
- Electricity and material sources, and soil transformation and occupation play significant roles as non-renewable exergy cost propagators and thus should be thoroughly analyzed not only during novel industrial plants lifetime but also for the future;
- By including soil exergy as a physical aspect of the plant's lifetime analysis sheds a light on how even renewable energy systems also have irreversible losses over time due to land occupation, transformation and loss of nature's work for the planet;
- When available on concentrations up to 15 vol% H₂, natural or geologic hydrogen can be an important decarbonized chemical feedstock alternative for stable and continuous hydrogen flow, presenting overall exergy costs competitive with renewable sources without requiring significant land occupation and soil degradation;

Preemptive studies involving load control optimization by dynamic analyses and mixing of hydrogen sources should be further investigated to mitigate significant non-renewable exergy footprint. For a global perspective, alternatives between sustainable agriculture, renewables production (by land occupation and transformation) and

biodiversity work should benefit the overall exergy consumption of a renewable ammonia plant without wasting non-renewable natural resources.

REFERENCES

- Alvarenga, R., Dewulf, J., Langenhove, H., & Huijbregts, M. (2013). Exergy-based accounting for land as a natural resource in life cycle assessment. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 18, 939–947.
- Aneke, M., & Wang, M. (2015). Potential for improving the energy efficiency of cryogenic air separation unit (asu) using binary heat recovery cycles. *Appl Therm Eng*, 81, 223–231.
- Bicer, Y., Dincer, I., Zamfirescu, C., Vezina, G., & Raso, F. (2016). Comparative life cycle assessment of various ammonia production methods. *J Clean Prod*, 135, 1379–1395.
- Blay-Roger, R., Bach, W., Bobadilla, L. F., Reina, T. R., Odriozola, J. A., Amils, R., & Blay, V. (2024). Natural hydrogen in the energy transition: Fundamentals, promise, and enigmas. *Renew Sust Energ Rev*, 189, 113888.
- Campbell-Stanway, C., Becerra, V., & Prabhu, S. (2025). Techno-economic analysis with electrolyser degradation modelling in green hydrogen production scenarios. *Int J Hydrogen Energ*, 106, 80–95.
- Carrasquer, B., Uche, J., & Martínez-Gracia, A. (2016). Exergy costs analysis of groundwater use and water transfers. *Energy Convers Manage*, 110, 419–427.
- Chatenet, M., Pollet, B. G., Dekel, D. R., Dionigi, F., Deseure, J., Millet, P., Braatz, R. D., Bazant, M. Z., Eikerling, M., Staffell, I., Balcombe, P., Shao-Horn, Y., & Schäfer, H. (2022). Water electrolysis: From textbook knowledge to the latest scientific strategies and industrial developments. *Chem Soc Rev*, 51, 4583–4762.
- Chehade, G., & Dincer, I. (2021). Progress in green ammonia production as potential carbon-free fuel. *Fuel*, 299, 120845.
- Comission, E. (2024). *Environmental life cycle assessment (lca) comparison of hydrogen delivery options within europe* (tech. rep.). European Comission.
- D'Angelo, S. C., Cobo, S., Tulus, V., Nabera, A., Martín, A. J., Pérez-Ramírez, J., & Guillén-Gosálbez, G. (2021). Planetary boundaries analysis of low-carbon ammonia production routes. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry and Engineering*, 9, 9740–9749.
- de la Hera, G., Ruiz-Gutiérrez, G., Viguri, J. R., & Galán, B. (2024). Flexible green ammonia production plants: Small-scale simulations based on energy aspects. *Environments*, 11, 71.
- EC & EEA. (2024). *The state of soils in europe* (tech. rep.). European comission (JRC), European Environment Agency.
- Fahr, S., Kender, R., Bohn, J.-P., Rehfeldt, S., Peschel, A., & Klein, H. (2025). Dynamic simulation of a highly load-flexible haber–bosch plant. *Int J Hydrogen Energ*, 102, 1231–1242.
- Granovskii, M., Dincer, I., & Rosen, M. (2007). Exergetic life cycle assessment of hydrogen production from renewables. *J Power Sources*, 167, 461–471.
- H2Europe. (2023). *Clean ammonia in the future energy system* (tech. rep.). Hydrogen Europe.
- IEA. (2024a). *Energy technology perspectives 2024* (tech. rep.). International Energy Agency.
- IEA. (2024b). *World energy outlook 2024* (tech. rep.). International Energy Agency.
- IRENA & AEA. (2022). *Innovation outlook: Renewable ammonia* (tech. rep.). International Renewable Energy Agency, Ammonia Energy Agency.
- Ishaq, H., & Crawford, C. (2024). Review of ammonia production and utilization: Enabling clean energy transition and net-zero climate targets. *Energy Convers Manage*, 300, 117869.
- Koschwitz, P., Anfosso, C., Bellotti, D., & Eppe, B. (2024). Exergoeconomic comparison of a novel to a conventional small-scale power-to-ammonia cycle. *Energy Rep*, 11, 1120–1134.
- Laimon, M., & Goh, S. (2024). Unlocking potential in renewable energy curtailment for green ammonia production. *Int J Hydrogen Energ*, 71, 964–971.
- Lima, A., Torres, C., & Valero, A. (2024). Circular thermoeconomics applied to a green ammonia synthesis plant: Future production scenarios and alternative byproducts. *Proceedings of ECOS 2024*.
- Lima, A., Torrubia, J., Torres, C., Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2025). Dynamic small-scale green ammonia non-renewable and renewable exergy costs up to 2050: Short and long-term projections under IEA energy transition scenarios. *Renew Energ (under review)*.
- Lima, A., Torrubia, J., Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2025). Non-renewable and renewable exergy costs of water electrolysis in hydrogen production. *Energies*.
- Mathur, Y., Moise, H., Aydin, Y., & Mukerji, T. (2025). *Techno-economic analysis of natural and stimulated geological hydrogen*.
- Mayer, P., Ramirez, A., Pezzella, G., Winter, B., Sarathy, S. M., Gascon, J., & Bardow, A. (2023). Blue and green ammonia production: A techno-economic and life cycle assessment perspective. *IScience*, 26.

- Mendrela, P., Stanek, W., & Simla, T. (2024). Thermo-ecological cost – system evaluation of energy-ecological efficiency of hydrogen production from renewable and non-renewable energy resources. *Int J Hydrogen Energ*, 50, 1–14.
- Mingolla, S., Gabrielli, P., Manzotti, A., Robson, M. J., Rouwenhorst, K., Ciucci, F., Sansavini, G., Klemun, M. M., & Lu, Z. (2024). Effects of emissions caps on the costs and feasibility of low-carbon hydrogen in the european ammonia industry. *Nat Commun*, 15, 3753.
- Mingolla, S., & Rosa, L. (2025). Low-carbon ammonia production is essential for resilient and sustainable agriculture. *Nat Food*.
- Müller, M., Pfeifer, M., Holtz, D., & Müller, K. (2024). Comparison of green ammonia and green hydrogen pathways in terms of energy efficiency. *Fuel*, 357, 129843.
- Musa, M., Hosseini, T., Sander, R., Frery, E., Sayyafzadeh, M., Haque, N., & Kinaev, N. (2024). Techno-economic assessment of natural hydrogen produced from subsurface geologic accumulations. *Int J Hydrogen Energ*, 93, 1283–1294.
- Palacino, B., Ascaso, S., Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2022). Exergy as an indicator to assess soil erosion. *Proceedings of ECOS 2022*, 1125–1136.
- Sánchez, A., & Martín, M. (2018). Scale up and scale down issues of renewable ammonia plants: Towards modular design. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 16, 176–192.
- Sciubba, E. (2024). A possible reconciliation between exergy analysis, thermo-economics and the resource cost of externalities. *Energy*, 132731.
- Smith, C., & Torrente-Murciano, L. (2024). The importance of dynamic operation and renewable energy source on the economic feasibility of green ammonia. *Joule*, 8, 157–174.
- Song, G., Chen, Y., He, Y., Jia, Q., Wu, Q., Cui, X., & Zhao, H. (2025). Techno-economic and life cycle greenhouse gas assessment of green ammonia produced by low-pressure haber-bosch process. *Energy Nexus*, 17, 100379.
- Sun, Z., Zhang, Y., Huang, H., Luo, Y., Lin, L., & Jiang, L. (2024). Modeling and simulation of dynamic characteristics of a green ammonia synthesis system. *Energ Convers Manage*, 300, 117893.
- Szargut, J. (1989). Chemical exergies of the elements. *Appl Energ*, 32, 269–286.
- Thomassen, G., Eswaran, A., Passel, S., & Dewulf, J. (2024). A planetary boundary for mineral, metal, and fossil resource extraction rates: How much primary materials can a circular economy extract? *Environ Sci Technol*, 58, 20345–20351.
- Tonelli, D., Rosa, L., Gabrielli, P., Caldeira, K., Parente, A., & Contino, F. (2023). Global land and water limits to electrolytic hydrogen production using wind and solar resources. *Nat Commun*, 14, 5532.
- Torrubia, J., Lima, A., Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2024). How renewable is green hydrogen? analysis of the exergy cost of its production. *Proceedings of ECOS 2024*.
- Torrubia, J., Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2023). Energy and carbon footprint of metals through physical allocation. implications for energy transition. *Resour Conserv Recy*, 199.
- Torrubia, J., Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2024). Non-renewable and renewable levelized exergy cost of electricity (lexcoe) with focus on its infrastructure: 1900–2050. *Energy*, 313, 133987.
- Valero, A., Palacino, B., Ascaso, S., & Valero, A. (2020). Towards an exergy methodology to assess the fertility of topsoil. *Proceedings of ECOS 2020*, 553–564.
- Valero, A., Palacino, B., Ascaso, S., & Valero, A. (2022). Exergy assessment of topsoil fertility. *Ecol Model*, 464, 109802.
- Valero, A., & Valero, A. (2014). *Thanatia: The destiny of the earth's mineral resources: A thermodynamic cradle-to-cradle assessment*. World Scientific Publishing.
- Wei, X., Sharma, S., Waeber, A., Wen, D., Sampathkumar, S. N., Margni, M., Maréchal, F., & van herle, J. (2024). Comparative life cycle analysis of electrolyzer technologies for hydrogen production: Manufacturing and operations. *Joule*, 8, 3347–3372.

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